

Green rice leafhopper resistance to malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate in Taiwan

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Green rice leafhoppers were collected from 10 sites throughout Taiwan in 1980. To measure susceptibility to the insecticides malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate, females were topically treated with the insecticide according to the FAO recommended method for the detection and measurement of insecticide resistance.

All populations showed various levels of resistance to malathion and methyl parathion (see table). Resistance ratios, as compared with data reported for the

Susceptibility to malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, permethrin, and fenvalerate of green rice leafhoppers in Taiwan.

Site	Resistance ratio ^a				
	Malathion	Methyl parathion	Carbaryl	Permethrin	Fenvalerate
I-lan	30	90	14	1.7	1.0
Hsin-chu	27	32	12	1.0	1.4
Dah4	250	226	79	5.5	1.0
Tsao-tung	408	235	74	2.1	1.4
Pai-ping	106	298	77	1.9	1.6
Pei-tung	288	326	37	4.9	1.9
Lu-ku	38	151	—	1.1	—
Chang-hua	225	172	47	2.9	2.3
Mei-nung	451	875	78	2.9	2.0
Ping-tung	368	554	24	2.2	1.5
Susceptible ^b strain	1	1	1	—	2.4

^aResistance ratio = LD₅₀ of each strain divided by LD₅₀ of susceptible or pertinent strain. ^bLD₅₀'s of malathion, methyl parathion, carbaryl, and fenvalerate against the susceptible strain were 0.57, 5.7, 0.71, and 0.34 µg/g, respectively. LD₅₀ of permethrin against Hsin-chu strain was 0.17 µg/g.

susceptible strain, ranged from 27 to more than 800. Resistance levels to carbaryl in these populations were somewhat lower, ranging between 12 and 79.

Permethrin and fenvalerate, two major synthetic pyrethroids recommended in 1980 for the control of this leafhopper, possessed higher inherent

toxicity to green rice leafhopper than the three conventional insecticides. Little, if any, resistance to the two synthetic pyrethroids was detected in the 10 multiresistant field populations, indicating no cross resistance between organophosphorus or carbamate compounds and synthetic pyrethroids. ■

Brown planthopper resistance to several insecticides in Taiwan

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The susceptibility to malathion, methyl parathion, MIPC, propoxur, permethrin, and fenvalerate of one susceptible (S), one malathion-resistant (R-mal), one MIPC-resistant (R-mipc), and four field strains of brown planthopper (BPH) from Taiwan was determined.

The 4th and 5th instars were sprayed with an acetone solution of insecticide. Toxicity of malathion, methyl parathion, and MIPC to the S strain was much lower than that of propoxur, permethrin, and fenvalerate (see table). The R-mal strain possessed some resistance to methyl parathion and MIPC. The R-mipc strain also showed some resistance to malathion and methyl parathion. Both R strains were significantly resistant to propoxur and permethrin, while remaining susceptible to fenvalerate. Field strains of BPH from heavily treated areas showed similar patterns of resistance to the six chemicals.

Susceptibility to 6 insecticides of 1 susceptible (S), 1 malathion-resistant (R-mal), 1 MIPC-resistant (R-mipc), and 4 field strains of brown planthopper in Taiwan.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml) S	RR ^a					
		R-mal	R-mipc	Ping-tung	Mei-nung	Chia-yi	Tai-chung
Malathion	0.023	1183	574	526	359	437	288
Methyl parathion	0.029	82	44	41	48	84	32
MIPC	0.021	22	41	14	15	18	10
Propoxur	0.0067	72	76	36	46	36	19
Permethrin	0.0058	171	122	74	121	83	71
Fenvalerate	0.0083	5	5	1.6	2.9	3.0	1.7

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of each strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

Field populations of BPH could not have been previously exposed to synthetic pyrethroids; therefore, the permethrin resistance detected must represent cross-resistance from insecticides used previously. These include organochlorine, organophosphorus, and carbamate

compounds. Susceptibility of all strains to another synthetic pyrethroid fenvalerate could be taken as an indication that in the BPH permethrin might have a mode of action or metabolic fate different from that of fenvalerate. ■

Acetylcholinesterase sensitivity and carbamate resistance in brown planthopper

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The sensitivity of acetylcholinesterases (AChE) of susceptible (S) and MIPC-resistant (R) strains of brown plant-

hopper to MIPC and several other carbamate insecticides was determined. The homogenate of 4th and 5th instars was incubated with a series of concentrations of insecticide solution. Residual activity of AChE was measured using acetylthiocholine iodide as substrate.

AChE of the R strain was 15.7-times less sensitive to MIPC than the S strain (see table). The R strain AChE also was

Sensitivity of acetylcholinesterases of susceptible (S) and MIPC-resistant (R) *N. lugens* strains to carbamate insecticides, Taiwan.

Insecticide	RR ^a	<i>N. lugens</i> strains		
		S	R	Ratio
MIPC	41	0.23	3.62	15.7
MTMC	80	5.86	18.0	3.1
Propoxur	76	0.15	1.10	7.3
Carbofuran	73	0.08	0.33	4.1
Carbaryl	41	0.38	0.92	2.4
Methomyl	33	6.99	29.4	4.2

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of R strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

less inhibited by several other carbamate insecticides.

A decrease of AChE sensitivity might be the primary cause of MIPC resistance in brown planthopper. A secondary cause is degradation of MIPC mediated by esterases, since a DEF inhibitor of these enzymes enhances the toxicity of MIPC to R strain. Insensitivity of AChE also contributed to brown planthopper resistance to several other carbamates. ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Integrated weed management in dry-land rice

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Weeds are a serious problem for direct-sown, short-duration, high-yielding rice-cultivars in Eastern India. This study involved 2 methods of sowing (broadcast and row), 3 seed rates (70, 90, and 110 kg/ha), 4 weed control treatments (nitrofen thiobencarb, propanil, and manual), and unweeded and untreated controls. The experiment was laid out in

a split-plot design with method of sowing and seed rate as the main plots and weed control and unweeded treatment as subplots.

Irrespective of seed rates, sowing in rows recorded higher plant populations, lower dry matter accumulation in weeds, and higher grain yield than broadcast method of sowing (see table). High seed rates recorded higher plant populations, lower dry matter accumulation of weeds, and higher grain yields than low seed rates.

Thiobencarb as a preemergence herbicide was slightly phytotoxic to rice, caus-

ing mortality of some seedlings. Maximum grain yield was obtained with propanil applied as split doses of 1.5 kg a.i./ha each at 15 and 30 days after sowing (DS) or high seed rate sown in rows. Manual weed control by hoeing once 15 DS and hand weeding 30 DS was next in yield. Propanil treatment reduced the dry matter accumulation in weeds from 324.7 g/m² to 68.8 g/m². Nutrient loss of 19.3 kg N/ha, 11.6 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 68.1 kg K₂O/ha in the unweeded control was reduced to 3.1 kg N/ha, 2.5 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 14.5 kg K₂O/ha with propanil. ■

Effects of sowing method, seed rate, and weed control treatment in Orissa, India.^a

Treatment	Plant population (no./m ²) 10 DS	Dry matter accumulation of weeds (g/m ²) 60 DS	Nutrient uptake by weeds (kg/ha) 60 DS			Grain yield (t/ha)
			N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
Sowing method						
Broadcasting	107.5	171.0	10.5	6.3	33.7	1.5
Row	143.5	156.8	9.0	5.4	25.9	1.8
Seed rate (kg/ha)						
70	115.6	151.8	9.6	5.6	33.1	1.6
90	128.4	142.6	8.1	4.9	30.8	1.4
110	146.4	104.1	6.1	4.9	23.9	2.0
Weed control method						
Nitrofen@ 1.5 kg a.i./ha 2 DS	150.7	151.5	9.0	5.4	31.9	1.6
Thiobencarb @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha 2 DS	112.0	166.6	10.7	7.0	41.4	1.2
Propanil @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha each 15 and 30 DS	158.0	68.8	3.1	2.5	14.5	2.8
Manual	146.3	76.9	4.6	2.8	16.4	2.1
Unweeded control	155.5	324.7	19.3	11.6	68.1	0.6
CD (0.05) for sowing method	20.6	7.3				0.04
CD (0.05) for seed rate	25.2	9.6				0.05
CD (0.05) for weed control method	11.2	16.4				0.09

^aDS = days after sowing.

Effects of herbicides and water management regimes on weeds and grain yields of transplanted rice in India

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The use of several herbicides under different water management treatments was tried in a replicated field trial at the Agriculture Research Station, Bhubaneswar, during the 1977 and 1978 wet seasons.

Continuous submergence had significantly the lowest weed population and weed weight (see table). Fluchloralin treatment showed promising effects on weed control at all the levels of water